

In the Lightscape of Quantum Information Holography (QIH), we embark on a mathematical sojourn, where the symphony of equations resonates in the unison of quantum mechanics, information, and gravity. The relation $hf = \hbar\omega = mc^2$ stands as the cornerstone in this theoretical construct, harmonizing these seemingly distinct domains into an integrated framework.

Wormhole Oscillations and Hawking Radiation:

Consider a pair of entangled black holes connected by a wormhole. The Hawking radiation emitted from the boundary of these black holes is imprinted on a qubit, transferring quantum information through the oscillatory behavior of the wormhole.

Equation 1: Oscillatory Behavior of Wormholes

$$\Delta\Psi_{\text{imprint}} = \int_{t_0}^{t_1} (2e^{i\omega_{\text{wormhole}}t}) \cdot \Delta\Psi_{\text{Hawking}}(t) dt$$

In this equation:

$\Delta\Psi_{\text{imprint}}$ represents the imprinted quantum state vector due to the wormhole's oscillations.

ω_{wormhole} signifies the angular frequency associated with the oscillations of the wormhole.

$\Delta\Psi_{\text{Hawking}}(t)$ represents the quantum state vector of the Hawking radiation emitted at a specific time t .

This equation encapsulates the dynamic interaction of wormhole oscillations and Hawking radiation, contributing to the quantum imprint on the holographic screen.

Quantum State Vector and Light Needles:

The imprinted quantum state vector acts as a light needle, encoding information through its angular disposition, θ .

Equation 2: Angular Disposition

$$\cos(\theta) = |\Delta\Psi_{\text{imprint}}| / (\Delta\Psi_{\text{imprint}} \cdot \hat{q})$$

Where:

$\hat{q}$ represents the reference quantum state (qubit axis).

This equation elucidates the probability encoding mechanism, where the cosine of the angle between the quantum state vector and the qubit axis determines the probabilistic outcomes.

Encoding Acceleration and Gravity:

The rate of change of the angle, θ , encapsulates the acceleration, which is synonymous with gravity in General Relativity.

Equation 3: Encoding Gravity

$$a = d^2\theta/dt^2$$

Where:

a is the encoded acceleration (gravity).

By capturing the acceleration in the quantum framework through the rate of change of θ , this equation bridges the realms of quantum mechanics and gravity.

Conclusion:

In the QIH framework, the elegant interplay of equations unveils the intricate tapestry of the universe, where quantum mechanics, information, and gravity waltz in a harmonious ballet. The triumvirate relation, $hf = \hbar\omega = mc^2$, reigns supreme, echoing the unity of these diverse realms, painting a comprehensive portrait of the cosmos through the mathematical brush strokes of QIH.